

Fluoro Complexes of Uranium(IV) Part IV The Far Infrared Spectra of Fluoro Complexes of Uranium(IV)

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The far i.r. spectra of several fluoro complexes of uranium(IV) have been studied in the metal halogen stretching frequency region ($500\text{--}300\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and have been compared with the i.r. band for uranium tetrafluoride and the available i.r. data of the fluoro complexes of actinides(V). The complexes of the type, $M^{II}M^{IV}F_6$ such as, $(\text{enH}_2)(\text{UF}_6)$ show the metal halogen vibrational band in the region $420\text{--}440\text{ cm}^{-1}$ as compared to 420 cm^{-1} in uranium tetrafluoride, and indicate that uranium(IV) ion in the hexafluoro complexes is 8-coordinated.

On the other hand complexes of the type, $M^I M^{IV} F_5$ such as $(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3)\text{UF}_5$ show the metal-halogen vibrational band at a higher frequency region, which are located in the range $460\text{--}470\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating a lower coordination number about uranium(IV) ion than the hexafluoro complexes. Most probable coordination number about the uranium(IV) ion in these complexes is seven.

The present study show that the complexes formed by the organic ammonium fluorides with uranium(IV) fluoride are significantly different from the alkali fluoride-actinide(IV) fluorides. The apparent differences are not, however, surprising but the effect of the large size of the organic ammonium groups.

A LARGE number of actinides(IV) fluoro complexes of the types, $M^I M^{IV} F_5$, $M_2^I M^{IV} F_6$, $M_3^I M^{IV} F_7$, $M_4^I M^{IV} F_8$, $M^I M_2^{IV} F_9$, $M^I M_3^{IV} F_{13}$, $M^I M_4^{IV} F_{17}$, $M^I M_6^{IV} F_{25}$, $M_7^I M_6^{IV} F_{31}$ and $M^{II} M^{IV} F_6$ (M^I = univalent cation, M^{II} = divalent cation and M^{IV} = Th, Pa, U, Np, Pu, Am and Cm) have been identified, though examples of each kind have not been known for all the quadrivalent actinide ions¹⁻⁵. The compounds of the type, LiMF_5 ($M = \text{Th, Pa, U, Np, Pu, Am and Cm}$) are of tetragonal symmetry, metal(IV) ions being 9-coordinated, but where the cation radius ratios lie within the range 0.99 and 1.64 no 1:1 complexes are formed. Such reported complexes are of the type, $M_7^I M_6^{IV} F_{31}$, possess rhombohedral symmetry and isostructural with $\text{Na}_7\text{Zr}_6\text{F}_{31}$, the structure is an eight coordinated array, six M^{IV} ions being arranged in a polyhedron which contains the additional fluorine atom. With relatively larger ions such as ammonium and rubidium ions both 1:1 and 7:6 complexes are formed and with still, larger ion such as, Cs^+ only 1:1 complexes are known.

The complexes of the type, KM_2F_9 ($M = \text{Th, U, Np and Pu}$) are isostructural with yttrium trifluoride; metal(IV) atoms being 9-coordinated. Complexes of the type, $M_2^I M^{IV} F_6$ exist in different forms, thus $\beta_2\text{-Na}_2\text{ThF}_6$ and $\beta_1\text{-K}_2\text{UF}_6$ possess structures as $M^I M_2^{IV} F_6$, where the M^{IV} ions are 9-coordinated, but $\alpha\text{-K}_2\text{UF}_6$ and $\gamma\text{-Na}_2\text{UF}_6$ possess respectively disordered

and deformed fluorite structures, the uranium atom being 8-coordinated. Complexes of the type, $M^{II} M^{IV} F_6$, such as, CaUF_6 , are all hexagonal possessing LaF_3 type structure, metal(IV) ion being 9-coordinated. In both, Na_3UF_7 and K_3UF_7 , uranium atom is 7-coordinated, and is situated at the centre of a pentagonal-bipyramid.

A number of fluoro complex salts of uranium(IV), with larger inorganic and organic base cations such as: hydrazinium, methylammonium, ethylenediaminium, pyridinium etc., have been reported by us earlier⁶⁻¹⁰. It was expected that fluoro complex salts containing these cations may give structurally different complexes because of their large size. We report here the far infrared spectra of these complex salts which have been carried out with a view to get information concerning coordination about the metal ion.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of E. Merck or B.D.H. quality. The compounds were prepared as reported earlier⁶⁻¹⁰. The i.r. spectra were recorded in Perkin Elmer model 221 spectrophotometer in KBr phase.

Results and Discussion

Infrared spectral data of the complexes are recorded in Table 1 (Fig. 1). Almost all these complexes show

TABLE 1—METAL-HALOGEN STRETCHING FREQUENCIES FOR FLUORO COMPLEXES OF URANIUM (IV)

Name and formula of the compound	$\nu(\text{U-F}) \text{ cm}^{-1}$
1. Methyl ammonium fluoride-uranium(IV) fluoride. (CH_3NH_3)(UF_5) H_2O	470s, b; 330s
2. Ethyl ammonium fluoride-uranium(IV) fluoride. ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_3$)(UF_5)	470s, b; 330s
3. Isobutyl ammonium fluoride-uranium(IV) fluoride. ($\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{NH}_3$)(UF_5)	470s, b
4. Benzyl ammonium fluoride-uranium(IV) fluoride. ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_3$)(UF_5)	465s, 320s
5. Ethylene diaminium fluoride-uranium(IV) fluoride. ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{N}_2\text{H}_6$)(UF_6)	420s, 320s
6. Propylene diammonium fluoride-uranium(IV) fluoride. ($\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{H}_8$)	425s 320s
7. O-phenylene diammonium fluoride-uranium(IV) fluoride. ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}_2\text{H}_8$)(UF_6)	440s 325s
8. Hydrazinium fluoride-uranium(IV) fluoride. (N_2H_5) UF_5	430s, b; 330s
9. Pyridinium fluoride-uranium(IV) fluoride. ($\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NH}$)(UF_5)	470s; 335s
10. α -Picolinium fluoride-uranium(IV) fluoride. ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{NH}$)(UF_5) H_2O	470s; 350s
11. β -Picolinium fluoride-uranium(IV) fluoride. ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{NH}$)(UF_5)	470s; 350s
12. γ -Picolinium fluoride-uranium(IV) fluoride. ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{NH}$) $_2\text{UF}_6$	470s; 380s; 340s
13. Anilinium fluoride-uranium(IV) fluoride. ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}_3$) $_2$ (UF_6)	465s; 320s, b
14. α -naphthyl ammonium fluoride-uranium(IV) fluoride. ($\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{NH}_3$)(UF_5)	465s; 330s, b
15. β -naphthyl ammonium fluoride-uranium(IV) fluoride. ($\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{NH}_3$)(UF_5)	460s
16. Quinolinium fluoride-uranium(IV) fluoride. ($\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{NH}$)(UF_6)	460s
17. Tetramethyl ammonium fluoride-uranium(IV) fluoride. (CH_3) $_4\text{N}$ (UF_5)	460s; V b
18. Disec-butyl ammonium fluoride-uranium(IV) fluoride. (C_4H_9) NH (UF_5) H_2O	470s; 340s, b

two bands, one in the region 400–500 cm^{-1} and the other in the range 300–400 cm^{-1} ; the high frequency band being more sensitive to structural changes.

Available information on the vibrational spectra of the halides and halide complexes of the actinides have been recorded¹¹. It is generally seen that a unit change of valency state of the central metal ion in the halo complexes, results in a change of 30–50 cm^{-1} in the position of the metal-halogen stretching vibration. An increased coordination within the same valency state results in a lowering of the metal-halogen vibrational frequencies.

The most obvious information that can be obtained from the present i.r. spectral data is that all the compounds believed to possess the stoichiometry, $\text{M}^{\text{IV}}\text{UF}_5$ show the $\nu(\text{M-F})$ band in the region 470 to 460 cm^{-1} . On the otherhand for the complexes having the stoichiometry, $\text{M}^{\text{IV}}\text{UF}_6$, the $\nu(\text{M-F})$ band is lowered by 30–50 cm^{-1} . Complete structures of the complexes are not known. But the i.r. spectral data unambiguously show that the complexes of the type $\text{M}^{\text{IV}}\text{UF}_6$ have a higher coordination number than the compounds of the type, $\text{M}^{\text{IV}}\text{UF}_5$ (except $\text{N}_2\text{H}_5\text{UF}_5$).

Fig. 1. I.R. spectra of:
(i) (CH_3NH_3) UF_5
(ii) ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_3$) UF_5
(iii) $\text{N}_2\text{H}_5\text{UF}_5$

The i.r. bands for the complexes of the kind, $\text{M}^{\text{IV}}\text{UF}_6$ are located in the region 440–420 cm^{-1} as compared to the position of the band for uranium tetrafluoride at 420 cm^{-1} . The $\nu(\text{M-F})$ band for the hydrazinium complex, $\text{N}_2\text{H}_5\text{UF}_5$, is also found at 430 cm^{-1} which is in good agreement with the value reported for this complex by Glavic and Slivnik¹². The coordination number about uranium atom in

TABLE 2—METAL-HALOGEN STRETCHING VIBRATION OF SOME ACTINIDE FLUORO COMPLEXES

Complex	$\nu(\text{M-F}) \text{ Cm}^{-1}$
NH_4PaF_6	444
K Pa F_6	454
Cs UF_6	503
K_2PaF_7	430
$\text{Rb}_2 \text{PaF}_7$	438
$\text{Cs}_2 \text{Pa F}_7$	438
(NH_4) $_2$ PaF_7	434
$\text{N}_2\text{H}_5\text{UF}_7$	435
UF_4	420

uranium tetrafluoride is eight. It seems most likely that for the complexes of the type, $\text{M}^{\text{IV}}\text{UF}_6$, and only for the hydrazinium complex, $\text{N}_2\text{H}_5\text{UF}_5$, the

coordination number about uranium atom is eight.

I.R. data are not available for tetravalent fluoro complexes of the actinides for further comparison. But some data are available for pentavalent actinide fluoro complexes and it may give useful information by comparison of these data with those of the pentavalent actinide fluoro complexes, since the position of the metal-halogen vibrational bands are closely related with the oxidation state of the central metal atom as well as the coordination number about it.

The i.r. spectra of the heptafluoro complexes, $M^I PaF_7$ ($M_2^I = K, Rb, Cs, NH_4$) where the protactinium atom is 9-coordinated are available (Table 2). For these complexes the metal-halogen stretching vibrations¹¹ are found in the region 430–438 cm^{-1} . For a 9-coordinated metal atom in uranium(IV) fluoro complexes, there would result a lowering of the metal-fluorine vibrational frequencies and would be expected to appear at 400 cm^{-1} . But a simultaneous decrease in coordination number by one unit, would compensate the effect of decrease in oxidation state; thus for a 8-coordinated uranium atom in the fluoro complexes of uranium(IV) such as; $(enH_2)UF_6$, the metal-fluorine vibrational band would be expected to appear at 430 cm^{-1} . The above analogy provides further support to our belief that coordination number about uranium in complexes such as $(enH_2)UF_6$ is eight.

The coordination number about the metal atom in complexes of the type, $M^IV UF_5$ seems to be lower than eight (*i.e.*, the coordination number about uranium atom in the $M^IV UF_6$ complexes) and obviously neither belong to the complexes of the type, $LiMF_5$ where the metal(IV) atom is 9-coordinated nor to the complexes of the type, $M_2^IV M_6^IV F_{31}$ where the M^IV atom is 8-coordinated. The metal-halogen stretching vibrations for these complexes $M^IV UF_5$ are located in the region 460–470 cm^{-1} , which are about 30–40 cm^{-1} above the region found for $M^IV UF_6$ complexes and 7-coordinated array about the metal(IV) ion appears to be most reasonable.

The i.r. data of the pentafluoro complexes of uranium(IV) may be compared with the i.r. data of the pentavalent actinide fluoro complexes with large alkali metal fluorides, such as caesium fluoride. The caesium fluoride-metal(V) fluoride complexes of the type, $CsM^V F_6$ ($M^V = U, Np$ and Pu) possess the $KOsF_6$ -type structure^{13,14,15} and in all these complexes, the metal(V) ions are in octahedral coordina-

tion. The $\nu(M-F)$ band for $CsUF_6$ is observed¹³ at 503 cm^{-1} . (Table 2). For a similar octahedral coordination about uranium(IV) ion in the pentafluoro uranates, the band would be expected at about 470 cm^{-1} . However, in our opinion the octahedral coordination would be rather low. On the other hand compounds of the type, $M^I M^V F_6$ ($M^I = K, NH_4$ and Rb ; $M^V = U$ and Pa) are isostructural and M^V ion is eight coordinated. Metal-halogen stretching bands for the protactinium complexes are located at 454–444 cm^{-1} . For 7-coordinated array about the uranium(IV) ion in $M^I U^IV F_5$ complex the metal-halogen stretching bands are expected to appear in the vicinity of this region. The observed value 460–470 cm^{-1} in the present series of complexes agree in a reasonably satisfactory way and provide further support in favour of a 7-coordinated array about uranium(IV) ion.

The above spectral data leads us to believe that the organic ammonium fluoride-uranium(IV) fluoride complexes show significant differences from the alkali metal fluoride-actinide(IV) fluoride complexes. This behaviour is not, however surprising but a consequence of the large size of the organic ammonium groups.

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